
"POETIC PARALLELS: AN ANALYSIS OF THE WORK OF ERKIN
VAKHIDOV AND SERGEI YESENIN"

Kodirova Ozoda

*is a teacher of the Department of Methodology of the Russian language,
Ferghana State University*

Annotation. The article analyzes the work of Uzbek poet Erkin Vakhidov and Russian poet Sergei Yesenin, revealing parallels in their poetic themes and style. Charming poets turn to the themes of love, adoration and philosophy, chilling lyricism and a philosophical approach to life. The images and motifs used by the poets are analyzed, and patterns at the junction of human life and existence are revealed.

Keywords: a mixture of life, poetry, poet, novel, philosophical subtext, comparative analysis of creations, lifestyle

Poetry is an expressive art capable of conveying our understanding of the world and human existence. In this context, a comparative analysis of the work of two outstanding poets - the Uzbek poet Erkin Vakhidov and the Russian poet Sergei Yesenin - is of particular interest. The comparison makes it possible to identify characteristic parallels between the ice ages, to identify common themes and stylistic features of glacial poetry.

Main themes and style features:

Erkin Vakhidov and Sergey Yesenin have gained fame for their lyrical works, in which they touch on topical issues of human life and existence. They address the themes of love, passion, philosophy and the mixing of life, using images and motifs close to the heart of every reader. The style of ice poetry is characterized by deaf lyricism, emotional urgency and philosophical overtones, which makes ice universal and understandable for people of different cultures and nationalities. A comparative analysis of the works of Vakhidov and Yesenin makes

it possible to better understand not only the poets themselves, but also those who support the human soul and his passion. Ultimately, exploring the parallels between the ice Ages can shed light on the universal values and ideals that unite people regardless of their cultural and national origin.

Scheme in style:

The poetry of Erkin Vakhidov and Sergei Yesenin acquires a number of common features in style, which make his work recognizable and attractive to readers.

1. Lyrical poetic language: charming poets use a simple, but at the same time deaf and emotionally urgent language that allows them to convey their feelings and thoughts. The ice Age is characterized by relative humidity and easy accessibility, which makes ice accessible to a wide audience.

2. Using images and motifs: Kurgan poets turn to images that tell about everyday life and human experiences in order to convey their emotions and memories. They use an image and a motif that shine and sing along with them, which makes poetry universal and relevant.

3. Metaphorical apparatus: Vakhidov and Yesenin often use metaphors and images to color deaf philosophical and emotional ideas. Ice metaphors are frequent and original, which makes ice poetry vivid and memorable.

The similarities in the poetry style of Vakhidov and Yesenin are that the Kurgan poet possessed a unique poetic talent and the ability to express syllabic ideas and feelings through the simple and vivid language of poetry.

Schemes in the subject:

The work of Erkin Vakhidov and Sergei Yesenin is thoroughly saturated with images and ideas that echo in icy poetry. Charming poets turn to eternal human themes such as love, passion, philosophy and a mixture of life.

Love: in everyday life, the poet expresses his feelings and memories of love through images and stories of everyday life. Vakhidov, like Yesenin, describes love as a strong and all-consuming feeling capable of overcoming all obstacles.

Parable: They turn to the parable as a source of thoughtfulness and wisdom. They describe bizarre landscapes and landscapes to convey their emotions and memories.

Philosophy: Vakhidov and Yesenin ask about the meaning of life, the meaning of death and the eternal cycle of time. The icy element of the Commonwealth is gnawing at philosophical considerations about being and being.

The meaning of life: per the answers to the question about the meaning of life and put the rival of the ex-heads of cities and districts, you are not poets, we are in our own creative work. They express their attitude to life and death, to the mystery of existence and human destiny.

An analysis of the work of Erkin Vakhidov and Sergei Yesenin allows us to draw significant parallels between poetry. Charming poets address the themes of love, passion, philosophy and the mixing of life, expressing their thoughts and feelings through images and symbols. Ice poetry was characterized by lyricism, a dull emotional charge and philosophical overtones. Drawing parallels between the works of Vakhidov and Yesenin is important for understanding poetic traditions and the interrelationships between cultures. It allows you to see common features in the poetic consciousness of different peoples and understand how literary traditions can influence and influence each other. Such a study can be explained mainly by Glinka's role in world literature and her role in shaping human cultural heritage.

Literature:

1. Sokolov A. N. Theory of style - M., 1968, Osmanov M. N. Style of Persian-Tajik poetry. In the IX-X centuries.-M., 1974;
2. Pospelov G. N. Problems of methodology and poetics. –M, 2003;
3. L.Alexey. The problem of funny style. 1994 Publishing house: "Collegium", "Kiev Academy of Eurobusiness".
4. E.Vakhidov is a great poet of the Uzbek people. / "Uzbek art and literature". 22-May, 2005.

